

THE ROLE OF TREES IN HUMAN LIFE

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Abstrakt. Har tomondan, atmosfera deb nomlangan havo qobig'i bilan o'ralgan. Atmosfera keng havo tizimidir. Atmosferaning yer ekotizimidagi ahamiyati odamlarni o'simlik dunyosi hayvonlari bilan hayot uchun zarur bo'lgan gaz elementlari (kislorod, karbonat anhidrid) bilan ta'minlashdan iborat. Havo turli gazlarning yig'indisidir. Ular orasida azot va kislorod asosni egallaydi. Quruq havo hajmining 78% azot, 21% kisloroddir. Boshqa gazlarning eng muhimi tutunli gazdir. Gazlardan tashqari, havo tarkibiga suv bug'lari, har xil turdagi chang kiradi. Atmosferaning pastki chegarasi aniq, bu er yoki suv yuzasi. Balandlik oshgani sayin havo yuqalashda davom etadi va oxir-oqibat asta-sekin global kosmosga o'tadi. Shuning uchun atmosferaning yuqori chegarasini aniq aniqlash qiyin. Birlashgan Millatlar Tashkilotining oziq-ovqat va qishloq xo'jaligi tashkiloti (FAO) mutaxassislari o'rmonlarning iqtisodiy rivojlanishdagi turli rolini qayd etishadi. O'rmon daraxtlari biologik xilma-xillik manbai hisoblanadi; ular suvni ushlab turishi mumkin; tuproqni barqarorlashtirish, ko'p miqdordagi uglerodni o'zlashtirish va kislorodni chiqarish va aholi punktlarining barqaror iqtisodiy rivojlanishiga hissa qo'shish. Bularning barchasi inson hayotining sifatiga ta'sir qiladi. Voyaga etgan kishi daqiqada taxminan 7 litr havo yutadi, deb ishoniladi. Agar siz ushbu raqamni kuniga daqiqalar soniga ko'paytirsangiz, siz 10 ming litrdan ortiq havoni yutasiz. Quyoshli kunda bir gektar o'rmon havodan 120-280 kg karbonat anhidridni yutadi va 180-200 kg kislorod chiqaradi. Bitta daraxt o'rtacha odamning 14% nafas olishi uchun etarli miqdorda kislorod chiqaradi. Bir gektar ignabargli o'rmonda 40 tonna chang, bargli o'rmonda esa 100 tonna chang bor. Daraxtlar karbonat anhidrid va suvdan glyukoza ishlab chiqarish uchun quyosh nuri energiyasidan foydalanganda kislorod chiqaradi. Ular uni boshqa o'simliklar singari o'zlashtiradilar, chunki ular metabolizmni tezlashtirish uchun energiya chiqarish uchun yana glyukozani parchalaydi. O'rtacha, 24 soat ichida daraxtlar ishlatilgandan ko'ra ko'proq kislorod ishlab chiqaradi, aks holda ular o'smaydi. Turkiston shahri va Turkiston viloyati keskin kontinental iqlim sharoitiga tegishli bo'lib, ularga Orol-Sirdaryo ofat zonasi salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatmoqda. So'nggi 50 yil ichida o'rtacha yillik harorat +1°C ga oshdi va yillik yog'ingarchilik 28 mm ga kamaydi. yiliga 225 kun qurg'oqchilik davri bo'ladi. Martdan noyabr oyining o'rtalariga qadar yog'ingarchilik miqdori oshdi va erning butun yuqori qatlami quridi. Changli shamol bir necha oygacha davom etadi. Yozda havo harorati 40-50°C ga etadi, quruq issiq shamol "kerimsal", qishda sovuq shamol "qora sovuq", bu nafaqat tashrif buyuruvchilar, balki mahalliy aholi uchun ham noqulay. Bugungi kunda o'rmonlar sayyoradagi eng muhim uglerod ombori hisoblanadi. Biroq, Qozog'iston past o'rmonli mamlakatlarga tegishli, 1 yil 2022 yanvar holatiga ko'ra respublikaning o'rmon qoplami mamlakat hududining 4,8 foizini tashkil qiladi. ularning maydoni 13,6 million gektarni tashkil etadi. Qozog'iston Prezidenti K. Tokayev xalqqa yo'llagan murojaatida 5 yil ichida respublikani keng miqyosda obodonlashtirish uchun o'rmon fondidagi aholi punktlariga 2 milliard daraxt va 15 million daraxt ekishni buyurdi, shu munosabat bilan ko'plab kapital ishlar olib borilmoqda.

Абстракт. Атмосфера представляет собой обширную воздушную систему. Значение атмосферы в экосистеме земли заключается в обеспечении человека газовыми элементами (кислород, углекислый газ), необходимыми для жизни растений и животных.

Воздух – это смесь разных газов. Среди них основные занимают азот и кислород. 78% объема сухого воздуха составляет азот, 21% — кислород. Помимо газов в воздухе содержатся водяные пары, различные виды пыли.

Эксперты Продовольственной и сельскохозяйственной организации Объединенных Наций (ФАО) отмечают разнообразную роль лесов в экономическом развитии. Лесные деревья являются источником биоразнообразия; они могут удерживать воду; стабилизация почвы, ассимиляция большого количества углерода и выделение кислорода, а также содействие устойчивому экономическому развитию населенных пунктов. Все это влияет на качество жизни человека.

Считается, что взрослый человек вдыхает около 7 литров воздуха в минуту. Если умножить это число на количество минут в день, вы вдохнете более 10 тысяч литров воздуха. В солнечный день один гектар леса поглощает из воздуха 120-280 кг углекислого газа и выделяет 180-200 кг кислорода. Одно дерево выделяет достаточно кислорода, чтобы среднестатистический человек мог дышать (14%). На один гектар хвойного леса приходится 40 тонн пыли, а в лиственном лесу – 100 тонн пыли. Деревья выделяют кислород, когда используют энергию солнечного света для производства глюкозы из углекислого газа и воды. Они поглощают ее, как и другие растения, потому что снова расщепляют глюкозу, чтобы высвободить энергию для ускорения метаболизма. В среднем за 24 часа деревья производят больше кислорода, чем используют, иначе они бы не росли.

Город Туркестан и Туркестанская область относятся к суровым континентальным климатическим условиям, на которые негативно влияет Арал-Сырдарьинская зона бедствия. За последние 50 лет среднегодовая температура увеличилась на +1С0, а годовое количество осадков уменьшилось на 28 мм. засуха бывает 225 дней в году. С марта до середины ноября количество осадков увеличилось и весь верхний слой земли высох. Пыльный ветер держится несколько месяцев. Летом температура достигает 40-50 С0, сухой горячий ветер «вреден», а зимой холодный ветер «черный холод», что некомфортно не только для приезжих, но и для местных жителей. Сегодня леса являются самым важным хранилищем углерода на планете.

Казахстан относится к малолесным странам, по состоянию на 1 января 2022 года лесистость республики составляет 4,8% территории страны. их площадь составляет 13,6 млн га. В своем обращении к народу Президент Казахстана К.Токаев поручил в течение 5 лет посадить 2 миллиарда деревьев и 15 миллионов деревьев в населенных пунктах лесного фонда для масштабного благоустройства республики.

Key words: oxygen, carbon dioxide, tons of dust, forest absorbs, liters, decorative and fruit plants, growth of tree, oxygen market.

Kalit so'zlar: kislorod, karbonat anhidrid, tonna chang, o'rmon, litr, manzarali va mevali o'simliklar, daraxt o'sishi, kislorod bozori

Ключевые слова: кислород, углекислый газ, тонны пыли, поглощает лес, литры, декоративные и плодовые растения, рост деревьев, рынок кислорода

Introduction. The earth is surrounded by a layer of air called the atmosphere. It is the outermost shell of the earth. The atmosphere is a vast air system.

The importance of the atmosphere in the Earth's ecosystem is to provide humans and animals with gas elements necessary for life (oxygen, carbon dioxide).

Air is a mixture of different gases. Nitrogen and oxygen take the place among them. 78% of the volume of dry air is nitrogen, 21% is oxygen.

The most important among other gases is carbon dioxide. In addition to gases, the air includes water vapor, various dusts. The lower boundary of the atmosphere is clear; it is the land or water surface. As the height increases, the air becomes thinner, and finally it gradually expands into global space. Therefore, it is difficult to define the upper boundary of the atmosphere.

Experts from the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) emphasize the diverse role of forests in economic development. Forest trees are a source of biological diversity; can store water; stabilizes the soil, absorbs a large amount of carbon and produces oxygen, contributes to the sustainable economic development of settlements.

All this affects the quality of human life. It is believed that an adult person inhales about 7 liters of air per minute. If you multiply this number by the number of minutes per day, you will inhale more than 10 thousand liters of air. On a sunny day, one hectare of forest absorbs 120-280 kg of carbon dioxide from the air and releases 180-200 kg of oxygen. One tree produces enough oxygen for the average person to breathe 14%. One hectare of coniferous forest holds 40 tons of dust, and deciduous forest holds 100 tons of dust.

Trees produce oxygen when they use energy from sunlight to make carbon dioxide and glucose from water. They absorb it like other plants because they break down glucose again to release energy to boost their metabolism. On average, in 24 hours, trees produce more oxygen than they use, otherwise they would not be able to grow.

Let's calculate the amount of pure O₂ produced by a large tree: For example, let's take a 40-meter tall sycamore. Such a tree produces up to 90 liters of oxygen per day, that is, 14% of a person's daily need. Thus, to provide a person with 100% pure oxygen, at least 7 big trees are needed.

Poplar grows quickly and forms a green leaf, one hectare of poplar produces 40 times more oxygen than one hectare of conifers. The oxygen released from one big tree per day is enough for 3 people to breathe during this time. Due to its wide and sticky leaves, the poplar perfectly protects from dust. Another advantage of poplar is that it grows very easily and quickly. Therefore, 1 is a poplar, 7 emits oxygen like a spruce.

After our standard of living increased, settlements were supplied with gas and water, many modern building materials appeared for construction, and after there was no demand for trees such as poplar and willow, such trees were not planted. On the contrary, the problem of planting conifers for decorative purposes has increased. In order to make our small area in front of the door beautiful, we do not allow plants to grow by laying pots (bruchatka) instead of green lawns! Of course, such situations must happen, because this is a requirement of life!

Today, in the era of globalization, the climate change that is happening all over the world is on everyone's mind. We know from information that many people are suffering from air pollution in big cities. It is better to think about the future of our Turkestan city from today!

Of course, many complex works are being carried out. Since Turkestan became the center of region, a lot of work has been done on planting trees under the name (Green Belt). At first there were many difficulties. Germination rate of planted seedlings was very low. The main reason is that most of the seedlings are matured in moist, fertile soils.

Due to the lack of adaptation to the climatic conditions of Turkestan, many seedlings withered after being planted. At the beginning, about 20 species and varieties of trees were planted, today only 4-5 species of those trees have grown in the territory of Turkestan and have a high

degree of growth; ailant, elm, catalpa, mulberry, acacia and berry trees. Therefore, these trees are mainly planted in recent years.

The city of Turkestan and the region of Turkestan belong to the emergency continental climate, which is adversely affected by the Aral-Syr Darya disaster zone. In the last 50 years, the average annual temperature has increased by +1C0, and the amount of annual precipitation has decreased by 28 mm. There are 225 days of drought in a year. From the month of March to the middle of November, the amount of evaporation increased from the amount of precipitation, and the entire upper layer of the earth dried up.

The dusty wind lasts for several months. In summer, the air temperature reaches 40-50 °C, dry hot wind - "harsh", in winter - cold wind - "black cold", all this is inconvenient not only for visitors, but also for local residents. The World Wildlife Fund (WWF) estimates that in 40 years, the biological resources of the planet Earth will be completely exhausted.

Forests can be destroyed in a matter of days and grow back in decades. Today, forests are the most important carbon store on the planet. However, their cutting and frequent fires are the cause of releasing a large amount of carbon dioxide into the atmosphere, which causes climate change processes and an increase in the average annual temperature on earth.

However, Kazakhstan belongs to countries with few forests. According to the Forestry and Wildlife Committee of the Ministry of Ecology, Geology and Natural Resources, as of January 1, 2022, the forest cover of the republic is 4.8% of the country's territory. and their area is 13.6 million ha.

The President of Kazakhstan K. Tokayev in his address to the people instructed to plant 2 billion trees in the forest reserve and 15 million trees in settlements within 5 years for the purpose of large-scale greening of the republic. No. 428-Z of the Prime Minister of the Republic of Kazakhstan dated 29.09.1993. to solve this problem, a new Botanical Garden with an area of 88 ha was established in the ancient city of Turkestan as part of the International Kazakh-Turkish University.

The creation of a botanical garden in the city of Turkestan had two goals: to create a scientific introduction center to study the assortment of decorative and fruit plants in the subarid region of South Kazakhstan, to establish an educational and production base for specialists in biology, ecology, and geography of the university.

The establishment of the botanical garden began in 1994. Today, the collection fund of the botanical garden includes 150 species and varieties of decorative and fruit plants, introduced here for the first time, brought from other regions, belonging to 59 genuses and 28 plans.

The greenhouse of the botanical garden was commissioned in 2012, and flowers were grown. Since 2018, seedlings have been grown using the method of rapid growth of decorative plants. Since the seedlings grown in the botanical garden are adapted to the climatic conditions of the Turkistan region, we are witnessing that the degree of germination of the planted seedlings is much higher than the seedlings brought from other places.

Therefore, it is of great socio-ecological importance to produce scientifically based species of other regional plants brought for introduction to arid conditions, and to form an effective technology for cultivation. That's why seed gardens for growing seedlings of several species of trees have been created and seedlings are being grown in the Botanical Garden today. The botanical garden also serves as a breathing park for city residents, because based on the above information, breathing becomes easier due to the high amount of bile required for human breathing. That is why we can say that the Botanical Garden is the lungs of the city of Turkestan.

The Minister of Ecology and Natural Resources of Kazakhstan, Yerlan Nysanbayev, specially visited the Botanical Garden of the Khoja Ahmet Usawi International University to get acquainted with the ongoing work, evaluated the work of the botanical garden with a history of almost 30 years, and noted that the Botanical Garden should be developed scientifically in the future. In addition, he proposed to widely use the possibility of the Botanical Garden to turn the southern region into a green area in the future.

In the future, the Botanical Garden has been turned into a special institute to carry out scientific work, as the minister mentioned. Our goal is to extensively study the types of trees in our collection that are adapted to our region and to introduce other drought-tolerant and heat-resistant types of trees from other countries. Due to the climate change that is happening all over the world, we are facing serious problems.

Drought is widespread, therefore, in the future, we should make the solution of this problem the main goal and determine the direction of our main scientific work.

President of Kazakhstan Kassym-Jomart Tokayev's Address to the People of Kazakhstan

If modern science is not used, agriculture will not just stagnate, but perish.

We widely use the achievements of not only our own, but also foreign scientists. I mean, not necessarily by directly adapting technologies and varieties to our own requirements. We, as scientists, should think about the solution of the problems expected 20-30 years in advance, predicting the future from today!

The main problem is the shortage of water, the warming of the air temperature, and the percentage of oxygen in the atmosphere is expected to decrease. Therefore, the most important issue is the breathing of humanity, what kind of air will we breathe in the future?

That is, the issue of health comes first.

Improving the living conditions of people in drought conditions, improving the environment and improving the climate are closely related to the creation of long-term sustainable forest plantations. It is no coincidence that the Government and the President of the Republic of Kazakhstan set before the foresters the task of carrying out large-scale works on growing artificial forests and increasing forest cover.

Solving the task in the case of the Turkestan region is complicated by a sharp continental climate and soils unfavorable for the growth of tree and shrub plants.

Forests play an important role in regulating the climate, regulating the distribution of precipitation, preventing wind erosion, etc. natural and artificial forests are important components of the biosphere, powerful regulators of biological balance in nature, play an important role in creating natural complexes and ecological conditions.

Forest plantations in field conditions provide blocking of deflation centers, change the landscape, serve as an element of permanent action against deflation, contribute to increasing the productivity of crops in adjacent fields for a long time, and protect them from shallow areas.

There is a connection between the sustainable development of the territory and the condition of the forest environment.

Thus, experts of the UN Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) note the different role of forests in economic development:

- forests reduce hunger and poverty, provide jobs and income, are a source of biodiversity, can store water, stabilize soil, and mitigate climate change by sequestering and storing large amounts of carbon;

- forests are very important in providing livelihood, income and employment of local population in non-agricultural activities related to processing of forest products, protection and fertilization of forests. Moreover, the oxygen market is emerging in the world, and it is quite possible that the price of oxygen on the market will be more expensive than the price of agricultural products in the next ten years.

Since oxygen is produced by forest trees, it may be wrong to directly associate this problem with the growth of our country. Of course, I may be publishing information that is not clear to you, but this is a requirement of life in the future. That's why we should take the issue of tree planting very seriously!

I invite you all to contribute to the growth of the number of trees in the country by fully contributing to the germination of the entire number of planted trees and using the latest techniques and technologies!

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